

IMPROVING WRITING SKILLS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article is about how to improve writing skills of students who has a drawback in it. Writing is a technical skill that allows you to effectively communicate through the written word. Though they may differ depending on what you're writing, there are a few that cross genres. Writing abilities can be more specifically defined as: spelling, grammar, structure and also vocabulary.

Kalit So'zlar: spelling, grammar, structure, vocabulary, read-aloud, cooperative learning, exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, resolution, and denouement.

It is paramount for mainstream educators to be knowledgeable regarding the education of English learners. One obstacle standing in the way of the success of ESL students is writing. Writing is a fundamental component of language. When a child writes, thoughts and knowledge are blended together creating a unique meaning. Consequently, students identify the skill of writing, as more difficult than listening and reading. Graphic organizers, cooperative learning, read-aloud, and group discussions are some strategies that can be used to accomplish this. Graphic organizers, for example, can be used as visual tools for students to write or draw what they already know about a subject. The type of writing that provides information or persuades others. Teachers can then determine whether additional instruction is required based on the results of this activity. Read-aloud, cooperative learning, and group discussions can help here. If necessary, a hand-selected text can be used to provide additional background information, potentially leading to group discussions. Cooperative learning is another excellent strategy for helping students gain more background knowledge, particularly for ELLs. This strategy necessitates students gathering information from books, the internet, or from one another. Writing is a skill that, like any other, can be improved with time and practice. Here are some tips for improving your written communication:

Get feedback.

Whether you're writing an email or an essay, soliciting feedback is a great way to see how someone other than yourself will interpret your text. Determine what you want your proofreader to focus on—the structure, conclusion, persuasiveness of an argument, or something else. Approach a reliable friend, family member, coworker, or teacher. If you're a student, your school may have a writing resource center where you can get help. Consider starting a writing group or enrolling in a writing class. Find writing classes online, at your community college, or at local independent writing workshops.

Write.

One of the best ways to improve your writing, like many other skills, is to practice. Here are a few ideas to get you started:

- Begin a journal or blog.
- Participate in a class or a writing workshop.
- Experiment with free writing.
- Send letters to friends and family.
- Create an opinion piece for your favorite local newspaper or publication.

Spelling basics and review grammar

The foundation of good writing is grammar and spelling. Writing with proper grammar and spelling communicates to your reader your professionalism and attention to detail. It also improves the readability of your writing.

Furthermore, knowing when and how to use less-common punctuation, such as colons, semicolons, and em-dashes, can open up new avenues for sentence structure and elevate your writing. Begin by consulting a writing manual if you want to improve your grammar and spelling. *The Elements of Style* by William Strunk and E.B. White has long been regarded as a writing bible. Similar resources can be found at your local library, bookstore, or online.

Think about structure

Grammar and spelling ensure that your writing is consistent and legible, but structure ensures that the main ideas are communicated to the reader. In many cases, forming an outline will aid in the solidification of structure. An outline can help you clarify what you want to convey in each section, visualize the flow of your piece, and identify areas that need more research or thought. Structure will vary depending on what you're writing. An essay usually consists of an introduction, several body paragraphs, and a conclusion. The six-stage plot structure may be used in fiction: exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, resolution, and denouement. Choose what is best for your needs.

Proofread.

While it may be tempting to submit work as soon as you finish it, make time to go over it again to catch errors big and small. Here are a few proofreading pointers to remember:

- Set aside your work before editing. Try to take a day or more away from your writing so you can return to it with fresh, more objective eyes. Are you short on time? Allowing yourself 20 minutes between writing and proofreading can help you approach your work with renewed vigor.
- Begin with simple fixes and work your way up to more significant changes. Starting with minor changes can help you get into a proofreading routine, allow you to reread your work, and clear distractions so you can focus on larger edits. Check your work for misspellings, inconsistencies, and grammar mistakes. Then, deal with any structural issues or awkward transitions.
- If you can express yourself in fewer words, do so. Being overly wordy can obscure your message and confuse the reader. Reduce redundant, repetitive, or obvious phrases.

To conclude, we may find lots of beneficial information when we want to learn writing essay or some kind article in social media. Writing effectively will enable you to communicate your ideas to the world, whether you are a scientist or a product manager, a journalist or an entrepreneur. With practice, exposure, and familiarization with basic rules, you'll be able to use your writing to say exactly what you want to say.

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